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Research Article

**A PROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS TO KNOW THE EFFICACY OF
SEALING CAPACITY OF THREE ROOT CANAL SEALERS**¹ Dr Muhammad Ans, ² Dr Adnan Zulfiqar, ³ Dr Fatima Tuz Zahara^{1,2} Margalla College of Dentistry, Rawalpindi³ Islamic Dental College, Sialkot

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this study was to evaluate the sealing capacity of three different sealants and to compare the sealing capacity of the three sealers.

Study design: A Prospective Study.

Location and Duration: This study was conducted in Margalla Dental Hospital, Rawalpindi for one year duration from February 2017 to January 2018.

Methods: 30 first mandibular premolar teeth single rooted were used. At the cemento-enamel junction, the crowns were removed and preparation of root canals were done for the K # 35 file. The teeth were divided randomly into 3 groups as A, K and R. Each group consisted of 10 samples.

Results: In Group A, AH Plus sealant, K group, Ketac-endo sealant and R group, Roth 801 sealant were used and using lateral condensation technique closed with gutta-percha. For one week, maintaining 100% humidity at 37 ° C, with nail polish the root surfaces were coated (spare the apex) and in a 2% methylene blue dye solution suspended for one week. In order to evaluate the following mean values of the dye penetration, the roots were divided into longitudinal sections, group A -2,675 mm, group K - 2,346 mm, group R - 4,929 mm.

Conclusion: This analysis proves that Ketac-endo provides better sealing than the Roth 801 sealer.

Key Words: Roth 801, Ketac-endo, AH Plus, Lateral Condensation, Apical sealing, root canal filling, dye Leakage.

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INTRODUCTION:

The main purpose of the endodontics is the total debridement of the pulp cavity, complete debritement of the root canals and the development of a liquid-tight seal in the apical foramen. To fill the root canals, two materials basically are used in combination. To fill most of the space, a solid core material is used and to fill the existing discrepancies between the walls of the root canal and the solid core a cementitious substance is used. A hermetic seal cannot be produced by a solid core alone in a desired manner. A full and three-dimensional filling requires the use of a root canal sealant. Leakage from a sealed root canal consists of gaps in the interface between the sealant and the dentin or sealant and the gutta-percha, or in the sealant. Therefore, the sealing ability of a root canal seal is largely dependent on the sealing capacity of the sealing material used. Zinc oxide eugenol-based sealing materials are the most widely used because they have been familiar with the profession of dentistry for a long time, ease of use and are less common than newer materials. However, the desire to achieve better results and to continue research by academics and producers resulted in new materials.

Ketac-endo, a polyalquenoate glass root canal sealer, was introduced in 1991 by ESPE (ESPE, GMBH and co KG, Seefeld, Germany) with superior sealing capacity. Many studies have shown that glass ionomer fillers provide a superior apical seal compared to other conventional root canal sealants. The glass ionomer sealant is capable of chemically bonding to the dentin surface. The glass ionomer sealant has a good degree of biocompatibility because it is well tolerated by periapical healing tissues. Improvement due to glass ionomer was completed and bone growth was achieved against cement surface within 28 days. The glass ionomer has been shown to have anticorogenic properties due to the fluoride release of the modern version of the silicates and perhaps the best restorative material that secretes fluoride. An epoxy-amine resin based sealant, AH

Plus (DeTrey, Dentsply), is presented as a root canal sealant. Previous generation sealing materials based on epoxy-amine resin were examined and proved to achieve good results in sealing capacity. The aim of this study was to evaluate the sealing capacity of three different sealants and to compare the sealing capacity of the three sealers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This Prospective Study was conducted in Margalla Dental Hospital, Rawalpindi for one year duration from February 2017 to January 2018. For this study, 30 freshly extracted first premolar mandibular teeth with single canal were included. The teeth had a decay or restoration and the orthodontic treatment was extracted. The teeth were stored in a solution of 0.5% chloramine. The tooth extract tissue was removed from the root with the nerve brush (xxfine, Maillefer Switzerland), file size 15K (COLORINOX, Dentsply, Maillefer, Switzerland) was placed in a channel to control the permeability until it became visible in the apical foramen. The rubber stopper was adjusted to the level of the root coronal end. To determine the root length measurement was taken. The working length is checked by subtracting 1 mm from the obtained previously. For all samples, the same method was used.

The instrumentation was performed using the reverse technique. 5.25% NaOCl was used as an irrigation agent for all samples during instrumentation.

Before start each instrument, 1 ml of 5.25% NaOCl was dipped.

With a needle of 25 gauge attached to the length of the root canal at the two-thirds of its length. A rubber stopper 2 was used longer than the working length by collecting a file size of 15K mm.

After the instruments were completed, the samples were divided into three groups with ten samples in each group. , K and Group R. labeling Groups A.

Roth's sealer

- It is the same as Grossman's original formulation with the substitution of **bismuth sub nitrate for bismuth sub-carbonate**.
- **Roth's 801** is an modern-day Grossman formula and its newer version is **Roth's 811**

The sample was washed with NaOCl solution after 5.25% instrumentation to maintain the same as the final discharge smear layer of three samples.

Group A, K and R samples were AH Plus, Ketac-endo and Roth respectively. Each group consists of 10 people.

In gasket distilled water, all samples were placed in individual plastic containers and soaked in a piece of gauze. With absorbent paper, each sample canal was dried (Dentsply, Switzerland) before sealing. According to the manufacturer's instructions the adhesive was mixed. A systemized gutta-percha cone (Switzerland, Mail-lefer Instruments SA, encoded colors) of the similar size as the main apical file were kept to the root canal, and the draw for each sample was verified. To maintain 100% moisture, in a separate containers with a wet gauze all samples were kept in and in an incubator at 37 ° C (Co, Schwabach + Memmert GmbH, Germany) for 1 week. After 7 days, each sample was dried. Then, with nail polish it was coated (USA Maybelline, Express finish,) and

covered with wax. After the nail varnish coatings were dried, the puff wax was removed. In airtight containers containing 10 ml of methylene blue solution (2%) the samples placed and at 37 ° C held in an incubator for 7 days. Then from the dye, samples were removed and washed with normal tap water. The fillings in the samples was discarded with a sharp object. The two root portions of each sample were imaged on an X30 magnifying stereomicroscope (Olympus, Japan) using an electronic digital caliper. Statistical analysis was performed in the 95% confidence interval using ANOVA, Scheff e test and Student's t test. ANOVA (Variance Analysis) was performed to determine the significance of the recorded values.

RESULTS:

In this study, the maximum linear penetration of the dye was measured to measure the relative leakage. The average values of dye penetration are given in Table 1.

Group	Apical leakage measurement (mm)			S.D
	Mini- mum	Maxi- mum	Mean	
A	0.00	4.84	2.675	1.7
K	1.00	5.66	2.346	1.4
R	1.30	8.85	4.929	3.3

TABLE 1: MINIMUM, MAXIMUM AND MEAN LEAKAGE VALUES IN MM WITH STANDARD DEVIATION.

Group A: Group A had an average value of 2.675 mm $\pm$ 1.7 and the leakage values ranged from 0.00 mm to 4.84 mm.

Group K: group K, mean leakage values ranging from 2,346 mm $\pm$ 1,4 to 1,00 mm to 5,66 mm

R group: The leakage values of the R group ranged from a minimum of 1,30 mm to a maximum of 8,85 mm, with an average of 4,929 mm $\pm$ 3,3.

The results showed that mean apical leakage values for group K were significantly lower than the R group ($P < 0.05$). The post-hoc analysis using Scheff's test showed that there was a significantly lower leakage in the K group compared to the R group, and there was no static variation in the mean values of the K group and A group. ($P > 0.05$). Similarly, the for group A mean values and group R did not differ significantly ($P > 0.06$).

DISCUSSION:

In this study, dye penetration technique with methylene blue was used to compare apical leakage. Linear measurement of the largest coronal extension of wall penetration was used to assess the sealing capacity of root canal sealants. This is a commonly used method to assess the sealing capacity of different materials and root filling techniques due to its simplicity. Advantages, non-destructive nature, leakage without the need for chemical reaction or exposure to hazardous radiation. This is a simple and direct method for evaluating apical microfiltration. A solution of two percent of methylene blue was used as a marker of leakage because it was not readily spreadable and could be readily detected under visible light, very soluble in water, not absorbed by the apatite crystals of the dental bone. Kersten and Moorer also suggested that methylene blue dye has a comparable leakage with butyric acid (the metabolic product of microorganisms). Paint penetration methods or radioisotopes were used in 82% of endodontic leakage studies. Matloff and colleagues have shown that methylene blue dye penetrates isotopes of channel markers, which gives a better representation of apical leakage. Ahlberg et al. methylene blue dye can act as a suitable leakage of microorganisms and endotoxin large and toxic low molecular weight. However, it has not yet been elucidated how the movement of the dye is compared with the movement of tissue fluid and in vivo bacterial migration. It seems reasonable to choose a technique that has proven to be the most effective in vitro testing. In this study, the Roth 801 sealant leaked significantly more than the Ketac-endo sealant. This finding was reported by Koch et al. The sudden adjustment of zinc oxide eugenol material (from a paste to a solid mass) may be responsible for the

separation of tensile walls or adhesive cracks caused by stresses caused by prosthetic contractions. This could explain the leak. The glass ionomer sealant can be attributed to minor leaks, adaptability and ability to bond to dentins, allowing the paint to penetrate less through the interface between the channel walls, cements and gutta-percha.

CONCLUSION:

The dye penetration studies results show the only relative sealing capacity of the in vitro root canal fillers and not demonstrate the ability of bacteria to inhibit riddling into complete radical channels in vivo. The use of radioisotopes, bacteria and dyes to assess leaks all have bad or good natural points. For the endodontic evaluation of leakage, there is no proper system. Studies should be evaluated with their scientific validity and values. Additional assays should be conducted to determine other features of a material such as biocompatibility, solubility, cleavage, radiopacity, and dimensional stability.

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